

The Role Of Metaphor In The Objectivization Of S. Moem's Emotional Competence In The Formation Of Rose Images

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Abstract: *This article examines the use of metaphor in S. Maugham's novel Cakes and Ale, or The Skeleton in the Cupboard as an associative mechanism in the construction of an impressionistic portrait, intended to evoke emotional response and to convey expressive characterization.*

Keywords: *emotive competence, cognitive metaphor, response, "tropic block," literary texts, emotional impact.*

1. Introduction

Somerset Maugham is known for his meticulously planned storyline, well chosen material, virtuoso command of the richness of sound and semantics in his home tongue, organic conversations, and his works' straightforward, frugal, and uncomplicated style. Maugham's writings are well-known and still important now because of the variety of characters, types, battles between good and evil, the horrible and the amusing, and so on. The writing style of Somerset's novels is superb. A philosophical and artistic examination of the timeless themes of existence—love, death, the essence of life and beauty, and the purpose of art—is obviously traced through the relationships, dreams, and aspirations of the main characters.

2. Methods

S. Maugham's novel *Cakes and Ale, or The Skeleton in the Cupboard* (1929) remains popular and widely read due to its enduring theme of creativity, its romantic plot, and Ashenden's emotionally charged perception of Drifffield's wife, Rosie. The stylistic fabric of Maugham's prose is marked by a high degree of metaphorical density, which is particularly evident in the construction of character portraits. Metaphor is known to function not merely as a descriptive device but also as a means of asserting individuality—an "invitation to a particular mode of world perception"—and as one of the manifestations of an individual linguistic worldview (Pavlyuchenko 1999:106). Within the scope of the present study, special attention is paid to the "tropic block" as a complex of figurative means that is most effectively realized in situations of Ashenden's perception of Rosie. Maugham repeatedly emphasized the significance of situational embedding in narrative, within which a character can evolve and exist, revealing their traits in a logically structured atmosphere: "But I had long had in mind the character of Rosie. I had wanted for years to write about her, but the opportunity never presented itself; I could contrive no setting in which she found a place to suit her..." (Maugham 1980:23).

Rosie's vivid and full-blooded personality, characterized by a rejection of the conventions of "respectable society," clearly required a corresponding emotional response. In the novel, this function of a "barometer" and a receptive, reflective instance is performed by the autobiographical character-narrator: "The Philip Carey of the earlier book became the I of *Cakes and Ale*" (Maugham 1980:24). Maugham foregrounds the reactions of the characters to Rosie's beauty as the primary means of generating the reader's emotive response. I. P. Pavlyuchenko defines the writer's emotive competence as "the ability, either

deliberately or intuitively, to employ a system of artistic devices in order to organize a variety of linguistic and stylistic emotive means with the aim of representing the author's emotional worldview in a literary text" (Pavlyuchenko 1999:47). In view of the above, it should be emphasized that S. Maugham deliberately draws on the extensive potential of the entire "tropic complex," as well as on the repetition of certain "key" lexical items, to create a dynamic, perception-based portrait of Rosie.

3. Results

It should also be noted that "the analysis of the immediate context of metaphor usage in discourse plays a significant role. Metaphor, in essence, does not exist outside context; for example, the word golden does not function as a metaphor until it appears at least in minimal contexts consisting of two-word combinations such as golden child, golden future, and the like" (Osokina et al. 2021:424). In the recurrent impressionistic portrait of Rosie, the word child functions as such a foundational metaphor: "She talked with a kind of eagerness, like a child bubbling over with the zest of life, and her eyes were lit all the time by her engaging smile ... like that of a child..." (Maugham 1980:70). The comparison with a playful child in this context emotionally generates the necessary associations of spontaneity, sincerity, vitality, charisma, and carefreeness, which attract those around Rosie and create a creative atmosphere for Driffield.

As T. G. Popova clarifies, "metaphor is very often interpreted as a 'compressed comparison,' as a kind of implicit or hidden simile. In other words, in the metaphorical process, one object, feature, or action is compared with another" (Popova 2020:69). The metaphorical complex associated with child is consistently expanded by the writer: "Mrs. Driffield gave me that childlike, mischievous smile of hers; she was perfectly at her ease" (Maugham 1980:83). The writer adds portrait details that create a sense of mobility in Rosie's facial expressions, her constant smile, cheerfulness of disposition, and her magnetism, which begins to attract the young Ashenden: "She looked at me with those soft blue eyes of hers in which there was a child's playful naughtiness... She looked at me with kindly shining eyes smiling with her full red lips" (Maugham 1980:66–67). The explicitly marked addressee of the smile (at me) is essential in this context, as it signals the beginning of the relationship between Rosie and Ashenden and functions as a recognition of the woman's beauty.

4. Discussion

Maugham further supplements the perceptual portrait with Ashenden's "discovery" of Rosie's beauty after contemplating her portrait painted by the artist Hilliard. It is important for the writer to emphasize that individual facial features do not constitute a standard of feminine beauty; rather, it is colour, harmony, and extraordinary vitality that together create the sensuous image of Rosie: "...but her eyes had the blue of cornflowers, and they smiled with her lips, very red and sensual, and her smile was the gayest, the most friendly, the sweetest thing I ever saw" (Maugham 1980:140). This mode of perception—realized through a series of epithets—clearly reveals Ashenden's personal attitude, enabling him to emphasize the uniqueness of Rosie's appearance.

The above is consonant with Catullus' poem dedicated to Livia, in which her beauty is defined simply yet comprehensively: "Here is Livia, fashioned whole from a single piece." It should be noted that Maugham's use of recurrent epithets in portrait construction is not accidental: "The epithet served as a preparatory stage for metaphor. The repetition of object nominations is based on the semantic interrelation between the defining and the defined object and its epithet... such an epithet was clearly motivated by those details that belonged to the object being described" (Maslova 2014:144). The contrasting nature of human relationships, capable of evoking entirely opposite impressions, is vividly illustrated by S. Maugham in his portrayal of Rosie. Ashenden, Rosie's lover, perceives her almost as a Virgin: "she was fulfilling the purposes of Nature, to embraces of lover," emphasizing, in a highly emotional and figurative manner, her naturalness, charm, and even her affectionate qualities as something inherently positive. In stark contrast, Mrs. Barton Trafford, who regards Rosie merely as a "buffet girl," a promiscuous woman who abandoned her husband, interprets her in entirely negative, metaphorical terms: "... it reminded her of a sacrificial

heifer” (Maugham 1980:141).

The final impression of Rosie’s character exemplifies Maugham’s metaphorical imagination, his subtle “play of the mind,” prompting readers to reinterpret metaphors such as “gold” and transform them into the epithet “gilded.” Rosie’s pursuit of wealth and her fondness for luxurious clothing—a fur coat costing 260 pounds, for example—are, in some sense, justified by her impoverished childhood. In America, the seventy-year-old Rosie aligns with contemporary standards and youth fashion; Ashenden notices the colors she wears, often too vibrant for her age (a frock of green chiffon heavily adorned with diamantes... her nails were blood-coloured). Yet, the one trait Rosie Iggalden never loses is her joy for life, her natural vivacity, and her childlike smile: “The only thing that remained was her smile, which had still its old childlike and mischievous sweetness” (Maugham 1980:187). This depiction of Rosie can be considered a “portrait in an interior.” Maugham presents the view of her drawing-room through the eyes of a successful English writer, with a subtle touch of irony. Recognizing Rosie’s modest cultural refinement and her taste as a consumer rather than a connoisseur, Ashenden notes her obsessive desire to furnish the room lavishly—Louis XV-style furniture, Sèvres porcelain, a bronze lamp—and the abundance of objects featuring gilt decoration or accents. It is important to the writer to convey Ashenden’s sense of amazement at the sight of the gramophone, which is also designed in the same style: “... all gilt shaped like a sedan chair and painted with Watteau courtiers and their ladies” (Maugham 1980:186). As we can see, it is the context that serves as the crucial formative element of the “authorial semantics” of a metaphor or epithet.

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